

In silico Association Analysis of GCK Gene Exonic Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms with Maturity Onset Diabetes of the Young

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ABSTRACT

Maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY) is a monogenic disease that is mainly characterized by β -cell destruction, impaired insulin biosynthesis, hyperglycemia, and a dominant autosomal mode of inheritance. It is mainly caused by gene mutations. The GCK gene is an essential gene for insulin biosynthesis. Any deregulation or mutation of this gene might result in MODY. Thus, nucleotide heterogeneity in this gene may be useful in identifying the probability of MODY occurrence. The purpose of the current study was to determine the impact of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the human GCK gene on various properties of the encoded protein, such as the extinction coefficient, aliphatic index, instability index, isoelectric point, half-life, transmembrane topology, subcellular localization, 3D configuration and ontology. For this reason, we first retrieved the coding sequence of the normal GCK gene transcript ENST00000671824.1 GCK-210 and forty-nine selected missense, frame-shift and stop-gain mutations by using the ENSEMBL database. We incorporated these SNPs into the normal GCK gene coding sequence and constructed a mutated coding region. Coding sequences of normal and forty-nine mutated GCK gene coding regions were transcribed into an amino acid sequence using the Translate tool-ExPASy. Then, changes in the function of proteins caused by SNPs were determined by changes in subcellular localization, ontology, 3D configuration and physical properties using CELLO2GO, PHYRE2 and ProParam-ExPASy tools, respectively. Pathogenicity analysis was also performed by using SIFT and PolyPhen tools. It was found that out of the forty-nine SNPs evaluated in the current study, eight variations documented in cases 3 (rs193922259), 11 (rs1554335752), 15 (rs193922295), 16 (rs1064796410), 19 (rs1470521850), 24 (rs104894006), 28 (rs144723656), and 32 (rs1562715426) considerably changed the physicochemical properties, 3D configuration and subcellular localization of mutated proteins. Among thirty-three SNPs, thirty were deleterious according to SIFT analysis. According to the PolyPhen tool, sixteen were probably damaging, thirteen were possibly damaging and one was benign. These genetic variations can potentially be used as biomarkers in humans to assess the likelihood of having MODY.

Keywords: maturity onset diabetes of the young, configuration, single nucleotide polymorphisms, mutations, gene, GCK, physicochemical

Introduction

Maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY) is a heterogeneous group of disorders (genetic, metabolic, and clinical) in which patients develop diabetes during adolescence or early adulthood (Kant et al. 2022). GCK-MODY is a subtype of MODY that can be represented as impaired glucose sensing of β -cells. It is caused by a heterozygous inactivating mutation in the GCK gene that leads to impaired pancreatic β -cell function and results in abnormal insulin production or excretion (Costa et al., 2000; Aarthy et al. 2021).

MODY accounts for 1–5% of all diabetes cases (Thanabalasingham et al., 2012) and 1–6% of pediatric diabetes cases (Hattersley et al. 2018). Its general population prevalence is 50–100 per million (Shields et al. 2010). GCK-MODY accounts for 30 to 50 percent of all MODY cases (Gardner et al., 2012). Its population prevalence is 1.1 in 1000 (0.1%) (Chakera et al, 2014). It accounts for 30% in Norway (Søvika et al., 2013), 36% in Denmark (Johansen et al., 2005), 32% in the UK (Shields et al., 2010), 83% in Poland (Fendler et al., 2012), 31% in Germany/Austria (Schober et al., 2009), 31% in the Czech Republic (Pruhovai et al., 2003), 63.4% in Italy (Lorini et al., 2009), 8.5% in Spain (Estalella et al., 2007), 63.6% in Japan (Yorifuji et al., 2012), 50% in Chile, 19% in Brazil, and 40% in Israel (Kanthimathi et al., 2014). Approximately 90% of MODY cases are misdiagnosed as either T1DM or T2DM (Ziegler et al., 2012). Factors such as misdiagnosed cases (such as other types of diabetes), undiagnosed cases and variable clinical ascertainment methods result in inaccurate MODY prevalence reports globally (Schober et al. 2009).

MODY symptoms include hyperglycemia, disease-onset age ≤ 25 , autosomal dominant mode of inheritance, disease transmission for at least three successive generations (Willer et al. 2010), control without insulin usage for at least five years, absence of ketonuria (Fajans 1990), absence of insulin resistance features, normal c-peptide range, and negative beta-cell antibodies (Juszczak et al. 2016). GCK-MODY is asymptomatic (Chakera et al. 2015), so clinical diagnosis is used for its detection (HULÍN et al., 2020). Clinical diagnostic criteria for GCK-MODY include mild fasting hyperglycemia (5.5–8.0 mmol/L), FPG in the range of 5.5–8.4 mmol/L (Steele et al. 2013), OGTT increment at 2 h is small (<3 mmol/L) and HbA1c values are just above normal 38–60 mmol/mol (5.6–7.6%) (Steele et al. 2013). Rare symptoms include microvascular and macrovascular complications (Steele et al. 2014; Rafique et al. 2021), polyuria, polydipsia, and weight loss (HULÍN et al., 2020; Tshivhase et al. 2021).

Normally, β -cells absorb glucose through glucose transporter type 2 (GLUT 2) present on their plasma membranes. Then, it is converted into glucose-6-phosphate (G6P) by the enzyme glucokinase (GCK), which then travels through glycolysis and the Krebs cycle for ATP synthesis. An increase in the ATP/ADP ratio shuts ATP-sensitive potassium channels (KATP) of the β -cell, preventing exocytosis of the potassium ions, which results in membrane depolarization. This depolarization leads to voltage-gated calcium channel opening, which results in calcium influx. This calcium influx stimulates the exocytosis of insulin by β -cells (Heuvel-Borsboom et al. 2016). Mutations in the GCK gene lead to impaired β -cell glucose metabolism (Heuvel-Borsboom et al. 2016), changing the insulin threshold and resulting in persistent hyperglycemia (Byrne et al. 1994).

MODY is a multifactorial trait and is influenced by genetic and environmental factors (Cappelli et al. 2011; Yahaya et al. 2020; Matejko et al., 2017; Li et al. 2022). Environmental factors are irregular dietary habits and a sedentary lifestyle (Matejko et al., 2017). The genetic factors include de novo and inherited mutations in one of the MODY-linked genes. MODY can be caused by one of the several types of mutations in one of 14 classified and 4 unclassified genes (Yahaya et al. 2020). Classified genes are hepatocyte nuclear factor-4 alpha (HNF4 α) (Li et al. 2008), glucokinase (GCK) (Reich et al. 2012), hepatocyte nuclear factor-1 alpha (HNF1 α) (Behar et al. 2010), insulin promoter factor/pancreatic duodenal homeobox (IPFI/PDX1) (Gibbs et al. 2010), hepatocyte nuclear factor 1 beta (HNF1 β) (Delaneau et al. 2012), Neurogenic differentiation 1 (NEURODI) (Holmkvist et al. 2008), krüppel-like factor 11 (KLF11) (Lee et al. 2012), carboxyl ester lipase/bile salt dependent lipase (CELL/BSL) (Li et al. 2008), paired box 4 (PAX4) (Morris et al. 2012), insulin hormone (INS) (Bjorkhaug et al. 2003), B-lymphocyte kinase (BLK) (Galan et al, 2011), ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 8

(ABCC8) (Aukrust et al. 2013), inward-rectifier potassium channel, subfamily J, member 11 (KCNJ11) (Bjorkhaug et al. 2000) and adaptor protein, phosphotyrosine interacting with PH domain and leucine zipper 1 (APPL1) (Ivanoshchuk et al. 2020). Unclassified genes include ISL LIM homeobox 1 (ISL-1) (Yahaya et al. 2020), regulatory factor X (RFX6) (Patel et al. 2017), NK6 homeobox 1 (NK6-1) (Mohan et al. 2018) and insulin receptor substrate 1 (IRS1) (Li J et al. 2020).

The GCK gene encodes glucokinase enzyme, a member of the hexokinase family, which is involved in carbohydrate metabolism and insulin secretion. It converts glucose into G6P in the cytoplasm of β pancreatic cells. It is the very first step of glycolysis (Osbaek et al. 2009). Its dysfunction leads to mild hyperglycemia, which contributes to MODY pathogenesis (Hulin et al. 2020; Ashcroft et al. 2023).

The major goal of the present study was to identify such single nucleotide variant mutations in the GCK gene that significantly alter the 2D and 3D structures, physicochemical attributes and subcellular localization of the mutated protein. As the GCK-encoded enzyme glucokinase has a strong association with MODY, abnormal enzymes might contribute to MODY. Therefore, variants causing dramatic alterations in glucokinase enzyme might be recommended for the prognosis and diagnosis of MODY in humans (Gersing et al. 2023). Keeping in mind this fact, the present analysis was designed to examine the impact of the reported GCK gene SNPs on the characteristics of the encoded protein. These SNPs may help in predicting and determining the predisposition of MODY in humans and can be further investigated through experimental analysis.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Retrieving the CDS of GCK

The GCK gene consists of 14 transcripts. This transcript consists of 11 exons and encodes a protein of 486 amino acids. The coding sequence (CDS) of this variant was retrieved from the Ensemble database (<https://asia.ensembl.org/index.html>, accessed on August 2022). The coding sequence of the normal GCK protein encoded by this transcript is shown in Supplementary data Figure 1.

2.2. Retrieving SNPs and Construction of Mutated CDS

Missense, frame shift and stop-gain SNPs of the GCK gene exonic region were retrieved from the Ensemble database. (<https://asia.ensembl.org/index.html>, accessed on August 2022).

2.3. Case design

Cases 1 to 49 were designed. For this purpose, a single SNP was incorporated into the CDS of the normal transcript to construct the mutated transcript.

2.3. Translation of CDS into protein sequence

The coding sequences of the wild-type and mutated genes were translated into amino acid sequences using the ExPASy tool (<https://web.expasy.org/translate/>, accessed on August 2022). A total of forty-nine mutated sequences were translated into amino acid sequences.

2.4. Assessment of deleterious status of SNPs

For the prediction of SNP effects on the stability of mutated proteins, SIFT and Polyphen tools (accessed on August 2022) were used.

2.5. Subcellular localization and ontology of wild-type and mutated proteins

For the prediction of SNP effects on the subcellular localization and ontology of mutated proteins, the CELLO2GO tool (<http://cello.life.nctu.edu.tw/cello2go/>, accessed on September 2022) was used. The results were obtained and compared with the subcellular localization and ontology of normal proteins.

2.6. Physicochemical Features

For the prediction of SNP effects on the physicochemical properties of mutated proteins, the PROTPARAM tool (<https://web.expasy.org/protparam/>, accessed on September 2022) was used. The physicochemical properties documented include the number of amino acids, molecular weight, theoretical pI, half-life, instability index, aliphatic index, and extinction coefficient.

2.7. 3-D and 2-D structures and transmembrane topology

For the prediction of SNP effects on 3-D and 2-D structures and transmembrane topology of mutated proteins, the Phyre 2 tool (<http://www.sbg.bio.ic.ac.uk/~phyre2/html/page.cgi?id=index>, accessed on September 2022) was used.

3. Results

3.1. Deleteriousness of SNPs

A total of forty-nine single nucleotide variants were documented in the present work. These variants included seven frameshift, twelve stop-gain and thirty missense SNPs (Table 1). According to SIFT analysis, thirty missense mutations were deleterious. According to the PolyPhen tool, sixteen mutations were probably damaging, and thirteen were possibly damaging (Supplementary data Table 1). Therefore, these human genetic variations can be used to assess their potential as biomarkers for MODY.

3.2. Effect of SNPs on the subcellular localization of proteins

No results were obtained for cases 1 & 2 when the mutated sequence was subjected to CELLO2GO, as the sequence was too short to be analyzed. Normal protein was observed to be localized in the cytoplasm with a value of 3.047. Mutations documented in cases 6-8, 10, 13, 14, 21-25, 27, 31, 38, 41, 43, 48 and 49 did not affect the subcellular localization of mutated proteins. However, the SNPs addressed in cases 3-5, 9, 11, 12, 15-20, 26, 28-30, 32-37, 39, 40, 42 and 44-47 caused the localization of mutated proteins to change from cytoplasmic to cytoplasmic and nucleated (Figure 1, Supplementary data Table 2).

3.3. Effect of SNPs on the ontology of mutated proteins

No results were obtained for cases 1 & 2 when the mutated sequence was subjected to CELLO2GO, as the sequence was too short to be analyzed. Among the forty-nine SNPs documented in the present study, ten variations were reported in cases 3 (rs193922259), 11 (rs1554335752), 14 (rs1583601365), 15 (rs193922295), 16 (rs1064796410), 19 (rs1470521850), 21 (rs34389297), 24 (rs104894006), 28 (rs144723656), and 32 (rs1562715426), which altered the ontology of mutated proteins considerably. Three cases of 30, 40, and 44 documented SNPs rs751505614, rs193922254, and rs777870079, respectively, caused slight changes in the ontology of mutated proteins (Supplementary data Figure 2).

3.4. Effect of SNPs on physicochemical parameters of mutated proteins

No results were obtained for cases 1 & 2 when the mutated sequence was subjected to PROTPARAM, as the sequence was too short to be analyzed. SNPs documented in cases 3, 11, 14, 15, 16, 19, 21, 24, 28, 30, 32, 35, 40-42, and 44 caused a change in the number of amino acids and molecular weight from normal values, i.e., 486 and 54385.89, respectively. The isoelectric point (pI) was observed to show the highest deviation from a normal value of 5.24 in cases 30 (5.61) and 35 (4.67). A slight change in pI was also observed in cases 3-4, 7, 8, 10, 11, 13-16, 18, 19, 21, 22, 24, 25, 28, 31, 32, 36, 38-42, 44, 45 and 48. Half-life did not show variation in any of the cases. The smallest and highest values of the extinction coefficient were observed in cases 11 and 30, i.e., 1490 and 64440 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. The instability index showed the highest and lowest deviations from the normal value in cases 16 and 35, i.e., 45.91 and 30.87, respectively. The aliphatic index was observed to be highest in case 3 (86.18) and lowest in case 21 (66.58) (Table 2).

3.5. Effect of SNPs on 3D structures of mutated proteins

No results were obtained for cases 1 & 2 when the mutated sequence was subjected to PHYRE2, as the sequence was too short to be analyzed. Among the forty-nine SNPs documented in the present study, ten variations were reported in cases 3 (rs193922259), 11 (rs1554335752), 14 (rs1583601365), 15 (rs193922295), 16 (rs1064796410), 19 (rs1470521850), 21 (rs34389297), 24 (rs104894006), 28 (rs144723656), and 32 (rs1562715426), which altered the 3D structure of mutated proteins considerably. Four cases, 30, 40, 41, and 44, documented SNPs rs751505614, rs193922254, rs866034131, and rs777870079, respectively, causing slight changes in the configuration of mutated proteins (Figure 2).

3.6. Effect of SNPs on the secondary structure of mutated proteins

No results were obtained for cases 1 & 2 when the mutated sequence was subjected to PHYRE2, as the sequence was too short to be analyzed. The highest value for the alpha helix was observed in case 3, and the lowest value was observed in case 30. The highest value for beta-turns was observed in case 32, and the lowest value was observed in case 3. The highest disorder (29%) was observed in cases 14 and 15. The lowest value (14%) was found in cases 7, 8, 17, 22, 23, 25-27, 29, 31, 33, 37-39, 43, and 48. Tm helix was observed in cases 8, 10, 12, 13, 23, 25, 29, 30, 39, and 45. The percentage ranged between 7 and 10 (Table 3).

3.7. Effect of SNPs on the transmembrane topology of mutated proteins

No results were obtained for cases 1 & 2 when the mutated sequence was subjected to PHYRE2, as the sequence was too short to be analyzed. Only two SNPs documented in cases 10 and 12 changed the transmembrane topology of mutated proteins, i.e., three domains were observed instead of two domains as in normal proteins. No effect on topology was observed in cases 8, 13, 23, 25, 29, 31, 39, 45, 47 and 48. On the other hand, no topology results were shown in the rest of the cases (Figure 3).

4. Discussion

MODY is a heterogeneous group of disorders (genetic, metabolic, and clinical) (Costa et al., 2000) with characteristic β -cell destruction, impaired insulin biosynthesis, fasting hyperglycemia, and a dominant autosomal mode of inheritance. It is a monogenic disease in which a patient develops hyperglycemia during adolescence or early adulthood (before 25 years of age) (Gardner et al., 2012). It is a rare type, accounting for 1–5% of all diabetes cases (Thanabalasingham et al., 2012).

Although mutations in the gene's promoter regions may have a strong impact on transcription of the gene (Gašperíková et al. 2009), mutations in the exonic region are more important because they may directly change the protein's structure and function. Therefore, the purpose of the current study is to ascertain the impact of polymorphisms located in the exonic region of the gene.

Polyphen is a bioinformatics tool that uses simple physical and comparative parameters to predict the effects of the substitution of an amino acid on the human protein structure (Zou et al., 2011). SIFT is a bioinformatics tool that analyzes a query sequence and predicts tolerated and deleterious substitutions for each position using information from several alignments (Ng et al., 2003). According to SIFT software, all missense mutations included in this study were deleterious. According to Polyphen software, 16 mutations were probably damaging, 14 were possibly damaging and one was benign. Similar studies were also present in the literature. In silico analysis reported in the Turkish population was carried out by using SIFT, Polyphen, and Mutation Taster bioinformatics tools (Aykut et al, 2018). Another in silico analysis in Turkish children was performed using SIFT, PolyPhen-2, and Align GVDG software. (Haliloglu et al, 2016). In silico analysis in Slovakian families was carried out by using SIFT, Polyphen, and Mutation Taster bioinformatics tools (Valentínová et al, 2012).

The function of a protein largely depends upon its subcellular localization. Translocation of a protein to its target site allows the protein to form essential interactions with its neighboring molecules so that it can take part in biological processes. Metabolic and

signaling processes depend upon the location and structure of the constituent proteins. If a protein with its original structure fails to reach its proper location (intracellular or extracellular), it will have a harmful effect on mutated proteins (Mer et al. 2013; Park et al, 2011; Casadio et al, 2008). Subcellular localization analysis performed by the CELLO2GO tool explained that SNPs addressed in cases 3-5, 9, 11, 12, 15-20, 26, 28-30, 32-37, 39, 40, 42 and 44-47 caused the localization of mutated proteins to change from cytoplasmic to cytoplasmic and nucleated. No such study predicting the effect of mutations on the subcellular localization of GCK protein has been found in the literature.

Another factor to understand the change in function due to SNPs is comparison of physical properties of mutated proteins with the normal protein. The present study demonstrated that the physical properties, i.e., molecular weight, isoelectric point, extinction coefficient, instability index, and aliphatic index, of mutated proteins were changed. The instability index is the measurement of the stability of a protein in vitro (Gamage et al., 2019). The instability index was observed to be highest in case 16 (45.91) and lowest in case 35 (30.87). The extinction coefficient is the measurement of the quantity of light a protein absorbs, which depends upon the protein concentration. The greater the extinction coefficient is, the greater the protein concentration (Note, A. 2013). The extinction coefficient was observed to be highest in case 30 (64440 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and lowest in case 11 (1490 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The "aliphatic index" refers to the proportion of a protein that its aliphatic side chains occupy. It indicates the thermal stability of a protein. A protein with a high aliphatic index is more thermally stable than protein with a low aliphatic index. (Panda et al, 2012). The aliphatic index was observed to be highest in case 3 (86.18) and lowest in case 21 (66.58). No such in silico analysis of the instability index, extinction coefficient, and aliphatic index has been found for GCK protein mutations in the literature.

Ontology analysis explained the impact of SNPs on molecular functions and biological processes. Molecular functions included ion binding and kinase, ATPase, hydrolase, and protease activities. Biological processes included small molecule metabolism and carbohydrate metabolism. If SNPs succeeded in altering the ontology of proteins, they also succeeded in altering the molecular functions and biological processes of the proteins. The molecular functions and biological processes of proteins change to the same extent as their ontology (Dessimoz et al. 2017). In the current study, ontology analysis of selected GCK gene SNP effects on mutated proteins was performed by using the CELLO2GO tool. This is the first study reporting the effect of variants on the localization of mutated proteins. No analysis has been reported in the literature.

To understand the effect of SNPs on protein function, we must look at the structure and function correlations of mutated proteins. SNPs altering the structure of the protein definitely alter the function of the protein. The function of proteins changes to the same extent as the structure does. The structure of proteins also revealed protein interactions with neighboring molecules (Sotomayor-Vivas et al. 2022). In this study, 3D structure analysis of normal and mutated proteins was performed using the PHYRE2 tool. The 3D structures of normal and mutated proteins were compared by the in silico method. According to our analysis, SNPs disturbed the 3D structure and thus might alter their function, as in cases 3 (rs193922259), 11 (rs1554335752), 14 (rs1583601365), 15 (rs193922295), 16 (rs1064796410), 19 (rs1470521850), 21 (rs34389297), 24 (rs104894006), 28 (rs144723656), and 32 (rs1562715426). A slight disturbance was also seen in cases 30, 40, 41, and 44, documenting SNPs rs751505614, rs193922254, rs866034131, and rs777870079, respectively. An in silico 3D structure analysis was also performed previously using the Modeler and GROMACS programs. According to this analysis, c.907C>T, c.460G>T, c.1339delC, c.781G>T, c.449T>A, c.775G>A, c.210A>C, c.1258A>G, c.562G>A, c.866A>G, c.834G>A, c.667G>A, c.1019+5G>A, c.120G>C, c.1345G>C and c.1182_1191de were not truncated but caused variation in structure (Capuano et al., 2012). A similar analysis was also performed using the Modeler and GROMACS programs. c.868G>T, c.115delA, and c.409C>G were truncated, while c.1358C, c.485G>A, c.369C>G, c.317_319delAGA, c.210A>C, c.502A>G, c.793G>A and c.394G>A were truncated. Although the literature reports in silico analysis of the effect of GCK gene mutations on MODY, the SNPs documented in the present study were investigated for the first time.

SNPs reported in cases 3 (rs193922259), 11 (rs1554335752), 15 (rs193922295), 16 (rs1064796410), 19 (rs1470521850), 24 (rs104894006), 28 (rs144723656), and 32 (rs1562715426) have a significant impact on the physicochemical properties, 3D configuration and subcellular localization of mutated proteins. Hence, they can be recommended as potential genetic biomarkers for GCK-MODY. These SNPs can be useful in identifying GCK-MODY risk.

Conclusion:

In the present study, variants in the GCK gene were found to alter the glucokinase enzyme structure and properties, which might result in its abnormal function. These SNP effects should be confirmed through experimental strategies in the future. Experimental work involving the comparison of GCK gene SNPs among normal and diseased individuals will provide proof of the association of these variants with MODY. In this way, we will be able to recommend these variants for use as potential biomarkers for MODY prognosis and diagnosis.

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Table 1: IDs, change in codon, position of codon, change in amino acid and consequence type of all the SNPs documented in the present study

Case #	SNPs ID	Change in nucleotide	Position on codon	Change in amino acid	Consequence type
1	rs1131691483	GAG>TAG	9	E>*	Stop gained
2	rs1281712444	CAG>TAG	24	Q>*	Stop gained
3	rs193922259	AGA>TGA	35	R>*	Stop gained
4	rs794727236	GAG>AAG	40	E>K	Missense
5	rs1562719705	CAT>TAT	50	H>Y	Missense
6	rs193922287	CCC>TCC	59	P>S	Missense
7	rs373418736	GGC>GAC	68	G>D	Missense
8	rs193922289	GGG>AGG	72	G>R	Missense
9	rs1554335761	GGT>AGT	80	G>S	Missense
10	rs193922290	AGG>TGG	85	R>W	Missense
11	rs1554335752	TGG>GG	99	W>X	Frame shift
12	rs762922697	GTG>ATG	101	V>M	Missense
13	rs193922292	TAC>GAC	108	Y>D	Missense
14	rs1583601365	TGC>TGA	129	C>*	Stop gained
15	rs193922295	TCC>TC	131	S>X	Frame shift
16	rs1064796410	CTG>CG	144	L>X	Frame shift
17	rs193922300	CCT>TCT	153	P>S	Missense
18	rs1170194230	GGC>GAC	162	G>D	Missense
19	rs1470521850	TGG>TGA	167	W>*	Stop gained
20	rs866388269	GGC>AGC	170	G>S	Missense
21	rs34389297	GCC>GC	173	A>X	Frameshift
22	rs886039380	GGG>GAG	178	G>E	Missense
23	rs193922306	GTC>GCC	181	V>A	Missense
24	rs104894006	CGA>TGA	186	R>*	Stop gained
25	rs1085307455	CGG>GGG	191	R>G	Missense
26	rs794727775	GCA>TCA	201	A>S	Missense
27	rs1441649062	ACG>ATG	206	T>M	Missense
28	rs144723656	TAC>TAG	215	Y>*	Stop gained
29	rs148311934	GTG>ATG	226	V>M	Missense
30	rs751505614	GAG>GG	237	E>X	Frame shift
31	rs1057524904	CGC>TGC	250	R>C	Missense
32	rs1562715426	TGG>TAG	257	W>*	Stop gained
33	rs1375656631	GCC>ACC	259	A>T	Missense
34	rs193929373	GGC>AGC	264	G>S	Missense
35	rs104894005	GAG>TAG	279	E>*	Stop gained
36	rs776328308	GGT>CGT	285	G>S	Missense
37	rs1554334905	GGC>AGC	316	G>S	Missense
38	rs1312678560	CGG>CTG	324	R>L	Missense
39	rs1230892001	GGA>AGA	349	G>R	Missense
40	rs193922254	GTG>TG	356	V>X	Frame shift
41	rs866034131	CAG>TAG	368	Q>*	Stop gained
42	rs780716926	CGA>TGA	379	R>*	Stop gained
43	rs104894016	GCT>CCT	399	A>P	Missense
44	rs77870079	TCG>TAG	404	S>*	Stop gained
45	rs1554334546	GGC>GAC	431	G>D	Missense
46	rs1562712097	GTG>GGG	448	V>G	Missense
47	rs193922278	ATC>AAC	457	I>N	Missense
48	rs193922280	GGC>GG	465	G>X	Frame shift
49	rs1057524900	GCG>GTG	475	A>V	Missense

Table 2: Prediction of SNP effects on the physiochemical properties of mutated proteins documented in the present study

Case #	No.of amino acids	Molecular weight	Isoelectric Point	Half Life (hr)	Extinction coefficient (M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ , 280 nm)	Instability index	Aliphatic index
Normal	486	54385.89	5.24	30	33640	40.78	76.40
3	34	4064.74	4.89	30	----	41.83	86.18
4	486	54384.95	5.33	30	33640	41.45	76.40
5	486	54411.92	5.20	30	35130	40.62	76.40
6	486	54375.85	5.24	30	33640	40.38	76.40
7	486	54443.93	5.19	30	33640	41.57	76.40
8	486	54485.02	5.29	30	33640	40.95	76.40
9	486	54415.92	5.24	30	33640	40.52	76.40
10	486	54415.91	5.19	30	39140	40.60	76.40
11	100	11373.00	4.98	30	1490	36.27	76.00
12	486	54417.95	5.24	30	33640	40.84	75.80
13	486	54337.80	5.19	30	32150	40.69	76.40
14	128	14736.82	4.86	30	9970	36.37	71.56
15	138	15872.13	4.96	30	15470	36.55	72.03
16	153	17716.34	5.47	30	15470	45.91	68.17
17	486	54375.85	5.24	30	33640	39.99	76.40
18	486	54443.93	5.19	30	33640	41.13	76.40
19	166	19188.05	5.32	30	9970	39.10	75.72
20	486	54415.92	5.24	30	33640	40.95	76.40
21	202	23524.98	5.49	30	43095	33.44	66.58
22	486	54457.95	5.20	30	33640	41.62	76.40
23	486	54357.84	5.24	30	33640	40.78	76.01
24	185	21118.25	5.47	30	15470	32.09	76.38
25	486	54286.75	5.19	30	33640	38.75	76.40
26	486	54401.89	5.24	30	33640	40.78	76.19
27	486	54415.98	5.24	30	33640	41.09	76.40
28	214	24408.05	5.37	30	17085	33.87	76.50
29	486	54417.95	5.24	30	33640	41.13	75.80
30	302	34172.10	5.61	30	64440	39.85	68.77
31	486	54332.84	5.19	30	33765	41.45	76.40
32	256	29107.26	4.87	30	20315	33.48	73.05
33	486	54415.92	5.24	30	33640	41.03	76.19
34	486	54415.92	5.24	30	33640	41.73	76.40
35	278	31635.98	4.67	30	27305	30.87	74.28
36	486	54485.02	5.29	30	33640	40.62	76.40
37	486	54415.92	5.24	30	33640	40.70	76.40
38	486	54342.86	5.19	30	33640	40.78	77.20
39	486	54485.02	5.29	30	33640	42.31	76.40
40	372	42142.87	5.12	30	35910	36.32	72.58
41	367	41496.06	4.88	30	30285	31.84	74.33
42	378	42712.50	4.88	30	31775	33.50	77.33
43	486	54411.93	5.24	30	33640	41.57	76.19
44	403	45460.62	4.97	30	32025	36.52	75.68
45	486	54443.93	5.19	30	33640	41.17	76.40
46	486	54343.81	5.24	30	33640	40.78	75.80
47	486	54386.83	5.24	30	33640	40.21	75.60
48	486	54858.37	5.34	30	50140	44.11	74.98
49	486	54413.94	5.24	30	33640	40.78	76.79

Table 3: Assessment of the effect of SNPs documented in the present study on the 2D configuration of mutated proteins

#	Case No.	Disorder (%)	Alpha helix (%)	Beta strand (%)
1	Normal	14	42	18
2	3	21	82	0
3	4	15	41	18
4	5	15	42	19
5	6	15	42	18
6	7	14	41	18
7	8	14	42	17
8	9	15	42	18
9	10	16	43	16
10	11	23	38	22
11	12	15	42	17
12	13	16	42	17
13	14	26	38	23
14	15	29	41	23
15	16	29	39	21
16	17	14	41	19
17	18	15	42	18
18	19	28	36	25
19	20	15	42	18
20	21	23	35	28
21	22	14	42	18
22	23	14	42	18
23	24	25	34	26
24	25	14	42	18
25	26	14	41	18
26	27	14	41	18
27	28	21	37	29
28	29	14	42	18
29	30	21	31	25
30	31	14	41	18
31	32	17	32	32
32	33	14	41	19
33	34	15	42	19
34	35	15	42	19
35	36	15	42	18
36	37	14	41	18
37	38	14	42	18
38	39	14	42	17
39	40	19	33	21
40	41	20	34	21
41	42	20	37	20
42	43	14	42	18
43	44	17	39	19
44	45	15	41	17
45	46	14	42	17
46	47	15	42	17
47	48	16	41	18
48	49	14	42	18

Figure 1: Prediction of the effect of SNPs documented in cases 1-40 in the present study on the subcellular localization of mutated proteins using the CELLO2GO tool. (Blue: extracellular, orange: plasma membrane, yellow: cytoplasmic, purple: cytoskeletal, dark green: endoplasmic reticulum, light blue: Golgi apparatus, light green: mitochondria, red: chloroplast)

Figure 2: Assessment of the effect of SNPs on the 3D configuration of mutated proteins documented in the present study using the PHYRE2 tool

Figure 3: Assessment of SNP effects on trans-membrane domains of mutated proteins documented in cases 10 and 12, predicted using the PHYRE2 tool